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A review: Liposome drug delivery system

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ABSTRACT

Liposomes are the smallest artificial vesicles of spherical shape that can be produced from natural untoxic phospholipids and cholesterol. Liposomes are concentric bilayered vesicles in which aqueous volume is entirely enclosed by a membranous lipid bilayer mainly of natural or untoxic synthetic phospholipids. Liposomes are extremely versatile due to the variability of their composition. However, their predominance in drug delivery and targetting has enabled them to be used as therapeutic tool in fields like tumour targetting, gene and antisense therapy, genetic vaccination, immunomodulation, lung therapeutics, fungal infections and skin care and topical osmetic products. By this topic we can know different innovative and unique technological formulations of liposomes for the different ailment of diseases.

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INTRODUCTION

Liposomes were discovered about 30 years ago by A. Bangham and since then they became very versatile tools in biology, biochemistry, medicine and subsequently became the most extensively explored drug delivery system. Rational research in drug delivery began in 1950's with the advent of polyclonal anti tumour antibodies developed for tumour targeting of cytotoxic drugs to experimental tumours.

This had triggered a series of concerted efforts evolved with the emergence of a plethora of delivery systems. As shown in the following schematic drawings of liposomes, the vesicles can be used as drug carriers and loaded with a great variety of molecules, such as small drug molecules, proteins, nucleotides and even plasmids¹.

Liposomes containing ingredients

Liposomes contains hydrophilic (water soluble) and hydrophobic (lipid soluble) ingredients.

PROPERTIES OF LIPOSOMES:

- 1) Liposomes are small, spherical vesicles which consist of amphiphilic lipids, enclosing an aqueous core.
- 2) The lipids are predominantly phospholipids (phosphatidylcholine) which form bilayers similar to those found in biomembranes
- 3) Depending on the processing conditions and the chemical composition, liposomes are formed with one or several concentric bilayers.

Classification²

Liposomes were first described in 1965 as a model of cellular membranes and quickly were applied to the delivery of substances to cells. Liposomes entrap DNA by one of two mechanisms which have resulted in their classification as either cationic liposomes or pH-sensitive liposomes.

1. Cationic liposomes: Cationic liposomes are positively charged liposomes and consist of co-lipid (helper lipids) which interacts with the negatively charged DNA molecules to form a stable complex. Commonly used co-lipids, required for stabilization of liposome complex include dioleoyl phosphatidylethanolamine (DOPE) or dioleoyl phosphatidylcholine (DOPC). One of the most frequently cited cationic lipids is lipofectin, commercially available cationic lipid first reported by Phil Felgner in 1987 to deliver genes to cells in culture.

2. pH-sensitive, or negatively-charged liposomes: As, both the DNA and the lipid are similarly charged, repulsion occurs rather than complex formation. In some cases, these liposomes are destabilized by low pH and hence the term pH- sensitive.

Cationic liposomes have been much more efficient at gene delivery both *in vivo* and *in vitro* than pH-sensitive liposomes. pH-sensitive liposomes have the potential to be much more efficient at *in vivo* DNA delivery than their cationic counterparts and should be able to do with reduced toxicity and interference from serum protein.

Different types of liposomes and their classification

Liposomes are often distinguished according to their number of lamellae and size.

1. Small unilamellar vesicles (SUV)
2. large unilamellar vesicles (LUV)
3. large multilamellar vesicles (MLV) or multivesicular vesicles (MVV)

SUVs show a diameter of 20 to approximately 100 nm. LUVs, MLVs and MVVs range in size from a few hundred nanometers to several microns.

Application of liposome

- Lipid Formulations for pre-clinical Application
- Formulation and preparation of lipid suspensions
- Making preformed vesicles.

Liposome characterization techniques

1. Light scattering
2. Fluorescent spectroscopy
3. Phosphorus/Nitrogen content
4. HPLC
5. Lyophilized lipid mixtures

Lippomix optisome

Lippomix innovative and unique technology provides effective delivery of selected locally acting therapies through topical application, i.e. to an isolated or localized area of the body. For such therapies, LIPPOMIX's platform delivery system:

1. Is superior to traditional systemic delivery (via ingestion or injection).
2. Delivers a greater quantity of a drug or active ingredient to the site of action (such as skin cells).
3. Reduces systemic side effects.

Liposome-encapsulated tetracaine anesthetic

The next lead candidate in lippomix's product pipeline is a topical anesthetic cream comprising optisometm encapsulated tetracaine (5%). This formulation was found to have a more rapid onset and a deeper anesthesia of longer duration, less variability between subjects compared to two currently commercial available products: EMLA (Astra), and Ela-MAX (Ferndale).

Transdermal liposomal formulations³

1. NSAIDS (Diclofenac, Ketoralac)
2. Topical anesthetics (Tetracaine)
3. Static anchored topical formulations such as anti-fungals
4. Anti-psoriatics, prophylactics and anti-microbials
5. Ablative release formulations such as DEET

6. Insect Growth Regulators, and
7. Anti-parasitics (Ivermectin)

Use of liposomes as injectable-drug delivery systems

Four major factors influence liposomes *in vivo* behavior and biodistribution like-

- (1) Liposome tends to leak if cholesterol is not included in the vesicle membrane.
- (2) Small liposomes are cleared more slowly than large liposomes.
- (3) The half-life of a liposome increases as the lipid dose increases and
- (4) Charged liposomal systems are cleared more rapidly than uncharged systems.

The most advanced application of liposome-based therapy is in the treatment of systemic fungal infections, especially with amphotericin B. Liposome's uses in cancer therapy include encapsulation of known antineoplastic agents such as doxorubicin and methotrexate, delivery of immune modulators such as N-acetylmuramyl-L-alanine-D-isoglutamine and encapsulation of new chemical entities that are synthesized with lipophilic segments tailored for insertion into lipid bilayers.

Liposome-based drug delivery in breast cancer treatment

Drug delivery systems offer the potential to enhance the therapeutic index of anticancer agents, either by increasing the drug concentration in tumor cells and/or by decreasing the exposure in normal host tissues. Theoretical barriers to drug penetration in solid tumors include heterogeneous vascular supply and high interstitial pressures within tumor tissue, particularly in necrotic zones.

Delivery of anthracyclines⁴

Anthracyclines exemplify the case of potent anticancer activity that is constrained by highly problematic systemic toxicities. For this reason, the most studied drug delivery applications in oncology have involved anthracyclines to preserve or to enhance efficacy against tumor cells while limiting exposure to critical target sites such as myocardium and bone marrow. Anthracyclines have been encapsulated in a number of liposomal

constructs. Current versions utilize ion trapping methods to achieve extremely efficient loading of doxorubicin or daunorubicin within the aqueous interior of unilamellar (single bilayer) liposomes, reaching 10⁴ drug molecules per liposome particle.

Polymer-based drug delivery represents another strategy to favorably alter the pharmacokinetics and biodistribution of derivatized drugs. One example is PK-1, a conjugate of the water-soluble, acrylamide-based, copolymer N-(2-hydroxypropyl) methacrylamide and doxorubicin. Polymer-based anthracyclines have not achieved the same degree of prolonged circulation as sterically stabilized liposomal doxorubicin.

Breast cancer involving the chest wall

A special problem in the management of advanced breast cancer is that of chest wall recurrence/metastasis, which is typically highly morbid and difficult to treat. Photodynamic therapy, in which systemically administered photosensitive compounds are activated by an external light source, can be considered a related strategy to drug delivery and is under investigation for the treatment of superficial breast tumors. In a multimodality strategy, hyperthermia (which is currently used to enhance the efficacy of external beam radiation for chest wall metastasis) has been used to modulate delivery of liposomal drugs.

In animal models, the application of hyperthermia to subcutaneous tumors concomitant with or prior to intravenous administration of long circulating liposomes results, in a marked increase in liposome accumulation within tumor tissue. The

Liposome in pulmonary delivery system^{5,6}

Major advantage of liposome as pulmonary drug delivery system is that they can be prepared from phospholipids that are endogenous to the lungs as components of lung surface. Currently the drug delivery to human respiratory tract is achieved by the principle types of devices like pressurized metered dose inhalers (PMDI).

Immunogenicity testing and protein engineering⁷

mechanism for this hyperthermia-enhanced liposome delivery appears to be via heat-induced changes in vascular permeability and microcirculatory dynamics, which further facilitate liposome extravasation from tumor vessels.

Liposomal Anthracyclines in Metastatic Breast Cancer:

Liposomal anthracyclines were developed to increase the therapeutic index of conventional anthracyclines by maintaining antitumor efficacy while improving the safety profile. There are currently three liposomal formulations: liposomal daunorubicin, liposomal doxorubicin (D-99), and pegylated liposomal doxorubicin. Only one phase I study has been conducted with liposomal daunorubicin for metastatic breast cancer.

Use of liposome in therapy of HIV infection or AIDS

Liposome may be useful in therapy of HIV infection in several ways-

1. Water insoluble drugs such as protease inhibitors may be solubilized in the membrane phase of liposome and delivered iv or sc. it is beneficial in delivery of protease inhibitors because of its low bioavailability.

2. Targeting liposome containing anti HIV drugs to cells and tissues infected with HIV 1 may enhance the efficacy and reduce the toxicity of the drug.

3. Large molecular wt. drugs such as antisense oligonucleotides may be delivered in cytoplasm of infected cells in encapsulated form may also provide protection against nucleases.

Antitope are pioneering a new generation of immunogenicity testing, antibody humanization, identifying T cell epitopes, producing humanized antibodies and generating non-immunogenic proteins and protein engineering technologies. Our mission is to apply these technologies to create improved non-immunogenic biologics.

Liposomes overcome problems inherent with viral vectors - specifically concerns of immunogenicity and replication competent virus contamination. The ability to chemically synthesize a wide variety of liposomes has

resulted in a highly adaptable and flexible system capable of gene delivery both in vitro and in vivo.

NON-VIRAL TECHNIQUES-

Delivery system

Viral Vector	Non-viral Techniques
Retrovirus	Liposomes
Adenovirus	Plasmid DNA
Adeno-Associated	Injection
Virus [↙] AAV [↗]	Ballistic DNA
Other Virus	Injection
	Other tech in vitro

Liposome offer several advantages in delivering genes to cells.

1. Liposomes can complex both with negatively and positively charged molecules.
2. Liposomes offer a degree of protection to the DNA from degradative processes.
3. Liposomes can carry large pieces of DNA, potentially as large as a chromosome.
4. Liposomes can be targeted to specific cells or tissues

CONCLUSION

The use of liposome in drug delivery have led to vastly improved technology in terms of capture, vesicle stability on storage, scale-up production and the design of formulation for special tasks. Remarkable advances have been made in understanding and controlling liposome behavior in vivo, this has facilitated the application of a range of liposomal drug in the treatment of diseases in experimental animal and clinically and in case of sterile production of liposome, reproductibility of preparation, pyrogen content, method of sterilization and its impact on the stability of the product, integrity of lipid, potentiality cost, quality control method and regulatory issues, as well as acute, subacute and chronic toxicity are seldom addressed.

The safety of liposome formulation must be specifically and categorically demonstrated. A comprehensive programme of relevant toxicity testing will be required before any liposome

formulation is accepted for widespread clinical investigation⁸.

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